

Supplement of

The need for open, transdisciplinary, and ethical science in seismology

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Supplement S1: Workshop program

From October 26 to 28, the early career scientists (ECS) and senior scientists of (not only) RISE, explored four cross-disciplinary topics: open science, transdisciplinarity, ethical implications, and dynamic risk. To address the objectives of RISE, the workshop focused on “Bringing research to practical applications that increase society’s earthquake resilience”.

We came up with the following workshop program which can be used by other groups to conduct a similar activity:

RISE Early Career Scientists Workshop

26–28 October 2022 in Naples, Italy

Overview

The workshop is planned by and for Early Career Scientists (ECS) of RISE with the purpose of exchanging ideas about ongoing and future research projects, interact, give context to our work, and getting to know each other better. Senior scientists are also welcome, especially on the last day when we present our ideas.

Our main theme is:

'Bringing research to practical applications that increase society's earthquake resilience',

which we will explore in four focus topics:

- **Transdisciplinary research:** integrate knowledge across academic disciplines and with non-academic stakeholders;
- **Open Science:** making scientific research transparent, collaborative, and accessible;
- **Ethical implications:** consider the ethical standards and their impact of people’s lives;
- **Dynamic risk:** appreciate the variability of seismic risk (time, location, and context).

More information about each focus topic and their related challenges in the chapter below (see [the four focus topics](#)).

Program

- **Day 1:** We will introduce each other in a round of lightning talks and listen to four keynote talks related to our focus topics.
- **Day 2:** We will collaborate in small groups to develop solutions (or improvements) for the challenges mentioned above. An off-topic activity in the afternoon will ensure that we recover from the creative thinking.
- **Day 3:** Each group will present its ideas to the senior scientists for expert feedback and identifying the next steps.

Day 1 – Wednesday, 26 October

Time	Event	Responsible
Introduction & Lightning talks		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Get to know each other</i> - <i>Identify synergies/common challenges/problems</i> 		
12:00–13:00	Welcome buffet & ice breaker	Organizers
13:00–15:00	<p>Workshop introduction [15min]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Objectives - Practical information - Schedule <p>Lightning talks [3min per person]</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Who am I? 2) What is my research focus? <p>Which of the four focus topics are relevant in your work? (see the four focus topics)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3) The four focus topics 4) What do you expect from the workshop? 	Organizers All
15:00–15:15	Break	
Keynote talks [20min presentation + 10min questions]		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Get inspired by the focus topics</i> - <i>Basis for building working groups</i> 		
15:15–15:50	<i>The journey to open and FAIR data in (EPOS) seismology</i>	Expert
15:50–16:25	<i>Sustainable software and data – Foundations and workflows for open and community driven development</i>	Expert
16:25–16:55	Coffee break with further discussions [30min]	
16:55–17:30	<i>Ethical and social aspects in the seismic risk reduction</i>	Expert
17:30–18:05	<i>Experiences from communicating with stakeholders to design products and services</i>	Expert
18:05–18:10	Wrap up + relation to the four themes	Organizers
Networking dinner [starting from 19.30]		

Day 2 – Thursday, 27 October

Time	Event	Responsible
Group work		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Holistically grasp the complexity of the theme and focus topics</i> - <i>Elaborate them in the group and then provide feedback to the other groups</i> 		
8:30–9:00	Introducing the four topics [10min] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Transdisciplinary research 2) Open science 3) Ethical implications 4) Dynamic risk Building the working groups [10min] Introducing the method [10min]	Organizers
9:00–10:30	Group Work - Draw your rich picture	Group work
10:30–11:00	Coffee break	
11:00–12:00	Rotating circuit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5min brief explanation of one group member - 10min feedback by the others [15min per group table → 60min; one person of each group has to stay and explain the rich picture]	Group work
12:00–13:00	Finalize the rich picture by integrating the comments of the other groups	Group work
Lunch break [13:00–14:00]		
14:00–17:00	Informal activity (e.g., excursion/guided tour)	
Free evening		

Day 3 – Friday, 28 October

Time	Event	Responsible
Group work & Feedback		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Recap the discussions from the previous day</i> - <i>Plenum discussion – bringing everything together</i> 		
8:45-9:00	Welcoming - Today's program	Organizers
9:00-10:00	Groups 1 & 2 presenting their rich pictures; with plenum discussion [per group 30min] - 2x 10min Presentation [talk through the rich picture] - 2x 20min Discussion	Groups (present & moderate)
10:00-10:30	Coffee break	
10:30-11:30	Groups 3 & 4 presenting their rich pictures; with plenum discussion [per group 30min] - 2x 10min Presentation [talk through the rich picture] - 2x 20min Discussion	Groups (present & moderate)
11:30-11:45	Take-away for RISE project	Project investigator
11:45-12:00	Next steps and final words - Good practice report - Opinion paper - Blog post - Future collaboration	Organizers
END		

The four focus topics

Topic 1 – Transdisciplinary research: integrate knowledge across academic disciplines and with non-academic stakeholders

Addressing societal challenges requires not only integrating knowledge from different disciplines (interdisciplinary), but also considering values, knowledge, know-how, and expertise from non-academic sources (transdisciplinary). For instance, this means to communicate with stakeholders from the society, co-design products/services, and test them with the end users.

More info: [What is transdisciplinary research?](#); [Ten steps to make your research more relevant](#), which were applied here: [RISE on the tracks of social relevance \(RISE newsletter #9\)](#)

Leading questions could be:

- *How to make our research transdisciplinary?*
- *How to communicate and interact with stakeholders from the society?*
- *How to tailor our products/services to the needs of our end users?*
- *How to ensure that our end users are able to take informed decisions and protective actions?*
- *What could decision makers expect from us? What can we provide? (i.e., authoritative tools)*
- *How can we involve citizens in our research efforts, and in turn, build trust? (being a scientist is not enough anymore to be trusted by the general audience)*
- *Which 'earthquake service' could the public demand most? What can we provide? (i.e., what does a citizen expect from us, if we present our project(s))*

Topic 2 – Open Science: making scientific research transparent, collaborative, and accessible

Open science envisions transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed collaboratively. It encompasses practices such as making research outputs open (e.g., open access, open data, and open source), rendering them verifiable and reproducible. This openness provides many additional benefits, for instance making it easier to publish and communicate scientific knowledge. Open science is guided by the FAIR Principles: ensuring Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets.

More info: [Wikipedia: Open Science](#); [European Commission: Open Science](#); [The Turing Way: Reproducible Research & Collaboration](#); go-fair.org/fair-principles

Leading questions could be:

- *How to encourage the use of open science practices?*
- *How to ensure source code sustainability?*
- *How to improve the completeness, sharing, and availability of data (e.g., among European countries)?*
- *How to collaborate more easily, effectively, and inclusively?*
- *How to evaluate research output more openly, qualitatively, and fairly?*

Topic 3 – Ethical implications: consider the ethical standards and their impact on people's lives

Ethical implications are relevant for collecting data and making data-driven decisions. Researchers have an obligation to consider them. Just to name some examples: the use of personal data according to GDPR, research truly sufficiently independent (of sponsors),

conflicts of interest, the responsibilities of scientists in respect of what is being done with their results, the duty to produce open science (which is a challenge when collaborating with industry/private companies), the potential misuse of data, products and services. Often these ethical issues also trigger legal implications (trials in L'Aquila, Italy in 2009 or in White Island, New Zealand in 2020).

More info: [Ethics Education in Science](#); [The Turing Way: Ethical Research](#)

Leading questions could be:

- *How to recognize and fulfill our responsibility (regarding personal data, communication, ...)?*
- *Which ethical issues are related to our work (e.g., use of personal data, responsibility of the services/products, misuse of data/models)?*
- *How can we address ethical implications of our research efforts?*

Topic 4 – Dynamic risk: appreciate the variability of seismic risk (time, location, and context)

The disaster cycle consists of five phases, namely mitigation, preparedness, emergency intervention, recovery, and reconstruction. The products/services that are developed within RISE contribute to various stages; however, how to combine them and do justice to the dynamic nature of risk needs to be explored further.

More info: rise-eu.org/dynamic-risk

Leading questions could be:

- *How to combine the different earthquake products/services (EEW, OEF, REI, RIA, AF, etc.) to maximize the contribution to disaster risk mitigation?*
- *How to deal with dynamic hazard and risk communication?*
- *What is the potential benefit of each product/service for the society?*
- *How to increase preparedness, ability to react during/after an event with our services?*
- *How to communicate discrepancies between multi-scale risk models (i.e., among European, national, and local models)*

Supplement S2: Rich Pictures drawn during the RISE ECS Workshop in Naples in October 2022.

We applied the Soft System Methodology to draw a rich picture for the three subjects (open science, transdisciplinarity, and ethics) and the overarching subject (dynamic seismic risk) which were defined in advance of the ECS workshop as emerging subjects to be considered when developing practical applications (Pohl, 2020). To this end, separate groups sketched their ideas on a rich picture (round 1), received feedback from the other groups (round 2), and revised it accordingly (round 3). In the following, the rich pictures for all three rounds are listed for the four issues.

S2a – Rich Picture for Dynamic Seismic Risk

Round 2

Round 3

Dynamic Risk

- ACRONYMS:
- EEW = EARTHQUAKE EARLY WARNING
 - REI = RAPID EARTHQUAKE INFORMATION
 - RIA = RAPID IMPACT ASSESSMENT
 - RLA = RAPID LOSS ASSESSMENT
 - OE(L)F = OPERATIONAL EARTHQUAKE (LOSS) FORECASTING
 - ALF = AFTERSHOCK (LOSS) FORECASTING
 - GDE = GLOBAL DYNAMIC EXPOSURE
- Stakeholders
- ☺ = public
 - ☒ = civil protection
 - ☒ = gov. / disaster manager
 - \$ = insurances
 - # = critical infr.
 - ⚙ = scientists
 - addressed in the future

- CHALLENGES AND PROPOSED SOLUTION
- TRANS-NATIONAL HAZARD MAPS
 - CONSISTENT GROUND-MOTION MODELS AT BORDERS
 - COMMUNICATE UNCERTAINTIES IN RIA/ LOW PROBABILITY IN OEF?

S2b – Rich Picture for Open Science

Round 1

S2c – Rich Picture for Transdisciplinarity

Round 1

S2d – Rich Picture for Ethics

Round 1

○ problems
 □ Solutions

that increase society's earthquake resilience?

Topic 3 – Ethical Implications: consider the ethical standards and their impact on data's uses

Ethical implications are relevant for collecting data and making data driven decisions. Researchers have an obligation to consider them. Just to name some examples: the use of personal data according to GDPR, research truly sufficiently independent (of sponsors), conflicts of interest, the responsibilities of scientists in respect of what is being done with their results, the duty to produce open science (which is a challenge when collaborating with industry/private companies), the potential misuse of data, products and services. Often these ethical issues also trigger legal implications (from the GDPR, Italy in 2019 or in White Island, New Zealand in 2019).

Note info: Ethics Education in Science: The Turing Way: Ethical Research

Leading questions could be:

- How to recognize and fulfil our responsibility (regarding personal data, communication, ...)?
- Which ethical issues are related to our work (e.g., use of personal data, responsibility of the services/products, misuse of data/intellect)?
- How can we address ethical implications of our research efforts?

○ problems
□ solutions

Do you think we should release earthquake probabilities and forecasts to the public?

Yes: |||
undecided: ||||
No: |

Topic 3 - Ethical implications: consider the ethical standards and their associated research. Ethical implications are relevant for collecting data and making data-driven decisions. Researchers have an obligation to consider them. Just to name some examples: the use of personal data according to GDPR, research truly sufficiently independent (of sponsors), conflicts of interest, the responsibilities of scientists in respect of what is being done with their results, the duty to publish open science (which is a challenge when collaborating with industry/private companies), the general issue of data, products and services. Other recent ethical issues also trigger legal implications, such as in L'Aquila, Italy in 2009 or in White House, New Zealand in 2020.

Put a line for your answer

People who don't care about ethics?

ethics

right and wrong

agreed upon

subjective

Communicating probabilities to the public?

How to enforce

publishing data handling → open science

- do nothing?
- vote?
- provide arguments

education

More Look for justification.

recruitment
more people in process =>

○ PROBLEMS
□ SOLUTIONS (POSSIBLE :-)

Supplement S3: Insight from an evaluation survey after the workshop.

After the workshop, we conducted a survey to evaluate the effectiveness of the activities, to collect a list with relevant products developed in RISE, and to assess preferences for advancing specific skills and expertise (N = 12). The outcome of the latter is shown in the Figure below: ECSs would especially like to receive practical knowledge on how to consider ethics and have a better understanding of societal stakeholders' decision-making processes.

Figure. Respondents' answers to the multiple-choice question "Which skills and expertise would you like to improve in order to advance your research?"